

PHARMAAYURVED ONLINE RESEARCH JOURNAL FOR PHARMACY, AYURVED AND ALLIED SCIENCES

<http://www.pharmaayurved.in/>

COMPARATIVE PHARMACOGNOSTICAL EVALUATION OF MARKET SAMPLE OF *TALISHADI CHURNA*

1. Richa Viradiya, Second year P.G. Scholar, Upgraded P.G. Department of Dravyaguna, Government Ayurved College, Vadodara, Gujarat, India
2. Dharmendra Jani, Associate Professor, Upgraded P.G. Department of *Dravyaguna*, Government Ayurved College, Vadodara, Gujarat, India

Citation: Richa Viradiya, Dharmendra Jani, (2024). COMPARATIVE PHARMACOGNOSTICAL EVALUATION OF MARKET SAMPLE OF *TALISHADI CHURNA* In Pharmaayurved Online Research Journal (Vol.8, Number 5, pp. 301–315). Pharmaayurved Online Research Journal. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14569086>

- **Corresponding author:** Dr. Richa Viradiya Email: rkviradiya294@gmail.com
- **Article Received on:** 21-12-24
- **Accepted on:** 24-12-24
- **Published on:** 26-12-24

Abstract

Background: *Talishadi Churna* is one of the important herbal formulations of ayurveda. It is a powder preparation made with the ingredients in the formulation composition given below. *Talisapatra* (*Abies spectabilis*), *Maricha* (*Piper nigrum* Linn.), *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Roxb.), *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.), *Vamsalochana* (*Bambusa arundinacea* (Retz.) Willd.), *Ela* (*Elettaria cardamomum* Linn.), *Tvak* (*Cinnamomum zeylanicum* Blume) and *Sarkara* (*Sachharum officinarum* Linn). To ensure the therapeutic efficacy and safety of herbal formulations and to justify their use in healthcare, standardization of these formulations is a crucial and necessary. **Material & Method:** Powder microscopy of *Talishadi Churna* procured from the local market of Vadodara, Gujarat, India was carried out. study was carried out at Pharmacognosy laboratory, Upgraded department of Dravyaguna Vijnan, Government ayurved college, Vadodara. Microscopic slides of *Talishadi Churna* were prepared using the required reagent and observed under the microscope. **Observation & Result:** Powder microscopy of *Talishadi Churna* shows, presence of profound Fragments of fibres, Sclerids and Epidermis with hypodermal cells beneath suggests that it contains *Talisapatra* (*Abies spectabilis*); presence of Sclereids, Pigment layer in surface view, Fragment of spiral vessels, Beaker cells in surface view, Hypodermal parenchyma cell, Prismatic crystals of calcium oxalate, Transversely cut beaker cells and Starch grains, suggests that it contains *Maricha* (*Piper nigrum* Linn.); presence of stone cells, Cork in surface view, Fragment of fibre with reticulated vessel, Cortical parenchyma containing starch grains and Reticulated vessel with pigment suggests it contains *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Roxb.); and presence Stone cells, Starch grains and Fragments of thin walled cells suggests it contains *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.); Epidermal cells, Parenchymatous cells of the perisperm with prisms, prisms, Sclerenchyma of testa (surface view and side view), and Starch grains shows presence of *Ela* (*Elettaria cardamomum* Linn.); presence of Phloem fibre, Part of fibre with phloem parenchyma, Sclereids and Starch grains shows presence of *Tvak* (*Cinnamomum zeylanicum* Blume) as its ingredients. But absence of oil globules suggest that exhausted ingredients can be adulterated with it. Presence of siliceous crystals suggests that it contains *Vamsalochana* (*Bambusa arundinacea* (Retz.) Willd.) but difficult to differentiate with highly adulterated silica.

Key Words:

Talishadi. Powder microscopy, Pharmacognosy, Powder microscopy, standardization of herbal formulations

INTRODUCTION:

The Ayurvedic medicine market has been experiencing significant growth over the past few years. More people are turning to natural remedies for wellness, leading to a greater demand for Ayurvedic products. Due to the growing demand for raw materials and the scarcity of resources, many manufacturers are forced to use adulterants and substitutes, which produces inferior products. The final product quality varies from pharmacy to pharmacy. Therefore, it is essential to ensure the therapeutic efficacy and safety of herbal formulations and to justify their use in healthcare, standardization of these formulations.

For the present study, one of herbal formulations of ayurveda, *Talishadi Churna* is selected. It is a powder preparation made with the ingredients in the formulation composition given below. *Talisapatra* (*Abies spectabilis*), *Maricha* (*Piper nigrum* Linn.), *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Roxb.), *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.), *Vamsalochana* (*Bambusa arundinacea* (Retz.) Willd.), *Ela* (*Elettaria cardamomum* Linn.), *Tvak* (*Cinnamomum zeylanicum* Blume) and *Sarkara* (*Sachharum officinarum* Linn). It is used in the Ayurvedic treatment of cough, cold, asthma, bronchitis, fever, vomiting, diarrhoea, bloating, anaemia, spleen diseases.¹ *Vamsalochana* is the siliceous materials generally found in the culms of bamboo. The silica is predominant in *Vamsalochana* and is substantially used as substitute and adulterant substance but there is no clear valid document to fulfil the use of it. The ingredients sodium silicate and ammonium silicate are used to make artificial *Vamsalochana*.² So, to ensure the quality and standards of the sample of *Talishadi Churna* procured from the market, along with the identification of characteristic feature of each ingredient of the combination in the sample, which enables us to identify the presence or absence of any adulterant and contaminant in the market sample.

AIM:

To study the powder microscopic features of *Talishadi Churna* procured from the local market of Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

OBJECTIVE:

1. To study the powder microscopic features of *Talishadi Churna* procured from the market of Vadodara, Gujarat, India
2. To identify and compare the assessed features of the *Talishadi Churna* with their standards of each of the individual ingredient mentioned in reference standard.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The sample of *Talishadi Churna* was procured from the local market of Vadodara, Gujarat, India in the month of October 2024. The study was performed at Pharmacognosy Laboratory of Upgraded Department of Dravyaguna Vijnana, Government Ayurved College, Vadodara, Gujarat.

Slide preparation:

Microscopic Slide of *Talishadi Churna* procured from the local market was prepared using required reagent (Safranin and Iodine) and observed under the microscope to assess their various microscopic identification. Microscopic characters observed were compared with the standards mentioned in reference standard.

OBSERVATIONS & DISCUSSION:**Table No. 1: Powder Microscopic features of *Talishadi Churna* found in local Market Sample**

NO.	Microscopic features	<i>Talisaptra</i>	<i>Maricha</i>	<i>Sunthi</i>	<i>Pippali</i>	<i>Vamsalochana</i>	<i>Ela</i>	<i>Tvak</i>	<i>Sarkara</i>
1.	Fragments of fibres	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-
2.	Sclereids	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	-
3.	Epidermis cells	+		-	-	-	+		-
4.	Prismatic crystals of calcium oxalates	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-
5.	Pigment layer in surface view	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
6.	Stone cells	-		+	+	-	-	-	-
7.	Starch grains	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	-
8.	spiral vessels	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
10.	Sclerenchyma of Testa	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
11.	Hypodermal parenchyma cell	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	-
12.	Beaker cells	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
13.	Cork cells	-		+	-	-	-	-	-
14.	Cortical parenchyma	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
15.	Reticulated vessel	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
16.	Sclerenchyma of testa	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
17.	pigment cell	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-

18.	Phloem fibre	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
19.	Siliceous Crystals	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
20.	Calcium oxalate crystals	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+

- Absent, + Present

Table No. 2: Microscopic features in reference standard³ compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Talisapatra (Abies spectabilis)* found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Talisapatra (Abies spectabilis)</i> in reference standard	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Fragments of fibres	+	Fig. 1(a)
2.	Sclerids	+	Fig. 1(b)
3.	Epidermis with hypodermal cells beneath	+	Fig. 1(c)
4.	Parenchyma cells filled with brown colour cell content	-	-
5.	Palisade parenchymatous fragments	-	-
6.	Xylem tracheids with spiral thickening	-	-

- Absent, + Present

Table No. 3: Microscopic features in reference standard⁴ compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Maricha (Piper nigrum Linn.)* found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Maricha (Piper nigrum Linn.)</i> in reference standard	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Sclereids	+	Fig. 2(a)
2.	Pigment layer in surface view	+	Fig. 2(b)
3.	Starch grains	+	Fig. 2(c)

4.	Fragment of spiral vessels	+	Fig. 2(d)
5.	Beaker cells in surface view	+	Fig. 2(e)
6.	Hypodermal parenchyma cell	+	Fig. 2(f)
7.	Prismatic crystals of calcium oxalate	+	Fig. 2(g)
8.	Transversely cut beaker cells	+	Fig. 2(h)

- Absent, + Present

No. 4: Microscopic features in reference standard⁵ compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Sunthi (Zingiber officinale Roxb.)* found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Sunthi (Zingiber officinale Roxb.)</i> in reference standard	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Stone cells	+	Fig. 3(a)
2.	Cork in surface view	+	Fig. 3(b)
3.	Fragment of fibre with reticulated vessel	+	Fig. 3(c)
4.	Cortical parenchyma containing starch grains	+	Fig. 3(d)
5.	Reticulated vessel with pigment cell	+	Fig. 3(e)

- Absent, + Present

No. 5: Microscopic features in reference standard⁶ compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Pippali (Piper longum Linn.)* found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Pippali (Piper longum Linn.)</i> in reference standard	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Stone cells	+	Fig. 4(a)
2.	Starch grains	+	Fig. 4(b)
3.	Fragments of thin-walled cells	+	Fig. 4(c)

- Absent, + Present

No. 6: Microscopic features in reference standard⁷ compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Vamsalochana ((Bambusa arundinacea (Retz.) Willd.)* found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Vamsalochana ((Bambusa arundinacea (Retz.) Willd.)</i> in reference standard	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Siliceous Crystals	+	Fig. 5(a)

- Absent, + Present

No. 7: Microscopic features in reference standard⁸ compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Ela (Elettaria cardamomum Linn.)* found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Ela (Elettaria cardamomum Linn.)</i> in reference standard	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Epidermal cells	+	Fig. 6(a)
2.	Parenchymatous cells of the perisperm with prisms	+	Fig. 6(b)
3.	prisms	+	Fig. 6(c)

4.	Sclerenchyma of Testa (surface view)	+	Fig. 6(d)
5.	Sclerenchyma of Testa (side view)	+	Fig. 6(e)
6.	Starch grains	+	Fig. 6(f)

- Absent, + Present

No. 8: Microscopic features in reference standard⁹ compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Tvak* (*Cinnamomum zeylanicum* Blume) found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Tvak</i> (<i>Cinnamomum zeylanicum</i> Blume) in reference standard	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Phloem fibre	+	Fig. 7(a)
2.	Part of fibre with phloem parenchyma	+	Fig. 7(b)
3.	Sclereids	+	Fig. 7(c)
4.	Starch grains	+	Fig. 7(d)

- Absent, + Present

No. 9: Microscopic features in reference standard compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Sarkara* (*Sachharum officinarum* Linn) found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Sarkara</i> (<i>Sachharum officinarum</i> Linn) in reference standard	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Crystals of calcium oxalate	+	Fig. 8(a)

- Absent, + Present

For this microscopic study, powder of *Talishadi Churna* was selected. The powder microscopic characters of *Talishadi Churna* were observed which will be narrated further. Powder microscopy of *Talishadi Churna* shows, presence of profound Fragments of fibres, Sclerids and Epidermis with hypodermal cells beneath identify that it contains *Talisapatra* (*Abies spectabilis*); presence of Sclereids, Pigment layer in surface view

Fragment of spiral vessels, Beaker cells in surface view, Hypodermal parenchyma cell, Prismatic crystals of calcium oxalate, Transversely cut beaker cells and Starch grains, identify that it contains *Maricha* (*Piper nigrum* Linn.); presence of stone cells, Cork in surface view, Fragment of fibre with reticulated vessel. Cortical parenchyma containing starch grains and Reticulated vessel with pigment identify it contains *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Roxb.); and presence Stone cells, Starch grains and Fragments of thin walled cells identify it contains *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.); presence of Siliceous crystals, identify that it contains *Vamsalochana* (*Bambusa arundinacea* (Retz.) Willd.); Epidermal cells, Parenchymatous cells of the perisperm with prisms, prisms, Sclerenchyma of testa (surface view and side view), and Starch grains shows presence of *Ela* (*Elettaria cardamomum* Linn.); presence of Phloem fibre, Part of fibre with phloem parenchyma, Sclereids and Starch grains shows presence of *Tvak* (*Cinnamomum zeylanicum* Blume) as its ingredients. But absence of oil globules suggest that exhausted ingredients can be adulterated with it.

CONCLUSION:

The local market sample procured from the markets of Vadodara, Gujarat, India, contains *Talisapatra* (*Abies spectabilis*), *Maricha* (*Piper nigrum* Linn.), *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Roxb.), *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.), *Vamsalochana* (*Bambusa arundinacea* (Retz.) Willd.), *Ela* (*Elettaria cardamomum* Linn.), *Tvak* (*Cinnamomum zeylanicum* Blume) and *Sarkara* (*Sachharum officinarum* Linn). Presence of siliceous crystals suggests that it contains *Vamsalochana* (*Bambusa arundinacea* (Retz.) Willd.) but difficult to differentiate with highly adulterated silica. Absence of oil globules suggest that exhausted ingredients can be adulterated with *Tvak* (*Cinnamomum zeylanicum* Blume).

Key identifications of features of *Talisapatra* (*Abies spectabilis*), *Maricha* (*Piper nigrum* Linn.), *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Roxb.), *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.), *Vamsalochana* (*Bambusa arundinacea* (Retz.) Willd.), *Ela* (*Elettaria cardamomum* Linn.), *Tvak* (*Cinnamomum zeylanicum* Blume), *Sarkara* (*Sachharum officinarum* Linn) are as follow;

Sr. no.	Plant	Key identification features
1.	<i>Talisapatra</i> (<i>Abies spectabilis</i>)	Fragments of fibres, Sclerids and Epidermis with hypodermal cells beneath
2.	<i>Marcha</i> (<i>Piper nigrum</i> Linn.)	Sclereids, Pigment layer in surface view, Fragment of spiral vessels, Beaker cells in surface view, Hypodermal parenchyma cell, Prismatic crystals of calcium oxalate, transversely cut beaker cells, Starch grains
3.	<i>Sunthi</i> (<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Roxb.)	Stone cells, Cork in surface view, Fragment of Fiber with reticulated vessel, Cortical parenchyma containing starch grains, Reticulated vessel with pigment

4.	<i>Pippali (Piper longum Linn.)</i>	Stone cells, Starch grains and Fragments of Thin-walled cells
5.	<i>Vamsalochana ((Bambusa arundinacea (Retz.) Willd.)</i>	Siliceous Crystals
6.	<i>Ela (Elettaria cardamomum Linn.)</i>	Epidermal cells, Parenchymatous cells of the perisperm with prisms, Prisms, Sclerenchyma of testa (surface view and side view)
7.	<i>Tvak (Cinnamomum zeylanicum Blume)</i>	Phloem fibre, Part of fibre with phloem parenchyma, Sclereids
8.	<i>Sarkara (Sachharum officinarum Linn)</i>	Crystals of calcium oxalate

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

The authors are thankful to Department of AYUSH, principal of Government Ayurveda College, Head of department, all faculty members, students and Co-workers of upgraded department of *Dravyaguna Vijnan*, Government Ayurveda College, Vadodara for their cordial support.

Plate No. 1: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Talishadi Churna – Talisapatra (Abies spectabilis)*

Fig. 1(a). Fragments of fibres

Fig. 1(b). Sclereids

Fig. 1(c). Epidermis with hypodermal cells beneath

Plate No. 2: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Talishadi Churna – Maricha (Piper nigrum Linn.*

Fig. 2(a). Sclereids

Fig. 2(b). Pigment layer
in surface view

Fig. 2(c). Starch grains

Fig. 2(d). Fragments of
spiral vessels

Fig. 2(e). Beaker cells in
surface view

Fig. 2(f). Hypodermal
parenchyma cell

Fig. 2(g). Prismatic
crystals of calcium
oxalate

Fig. 2(h). Transversely cut
beaker cells

Plate No. 3: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Talishadi Churna – Sunthi (Zingiber officinale Roxb.)*

Fig. 3(a). Stone cells

Fig. 3(b) Cork in surface view

Fig. 3(c). Fragment of fibre with reticulated vessel

Fig. 3(d). Cortical parenchyma containing starch grains

Fig. 3(e). Reticulated vessel with pigment cell

Plate No. 4: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Talishadi Churna – Pippali (Piper longum Linn.)*

Fig. 4(a). Stone cells

Fig. 4(b). Starch grains

Fig. 4(c). Fragments of thin-walled cells

Plate No. 5: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Talishadi Churna* – *Vamsalochana* (*Bambusa arundinacea* (Retz.) Willd.)

Fig. 5(a). Siliceous Crystals

Plate No. 6: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Talishadi Churna* – *Ela* (*Elettaria cardamomum* Linn.)

Fig. 6(a). Epidermal cells

Fig. 6(b). Parenchymatous cells of the perisperm with prisms

Fig. 6(c). Prisms

Fig. 6(d). Sclerenchyma of testa (surface view)

Fig. 6(e). Sclerenchyma of testa (side view)

Fig. 6(f). Starch grains

Plate No. 7: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Talishadi Churna – Tvak (Cinnamomum zeylanicum Blume)*

Fig. 7(a). Phloem fibres

Fig. 7(b). Part of fibre with phloem parenchyma

Fig. 7(c). Sclereids

Fig. 7(d). Starch grains

Plate No. 8: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Talishadi Churna – Sarkara (Sachharum officinarum Linn)*

Fig. 8(a). Crystals of calcium oxalate

REFERENCES:

1. Charak chikitsa sthana 8/145-148
2. Acharya Balkrishna et al., Vanshlochan Substitution and Adulteration: Discussions on the Controversy over its Original Source, *Ayushdhara*, July-August 2023, Vol 10, Issue 4, September 2023, ISSN: 2393-9583 (P)/ 2393- 9591 (O)
3. AFI,PART -1,7:13, A.K. Gupta, Quality standards of indian medicinal plants, Indian council of medical research, Vol 8, P.n.4
4. A.K. Gupta, Quality standards of indian medicinal plants, Indian council of medical research, Vol 8, P.n.258
5. A.K. Gupta, Quality standards of indian medicinal plants, Indian council of medical research, Vol 8, P.n.350
6. A.K. Gupta, Quality standards of indian medicinal plants, Indian council of medical research, Vol 1, P.n.169
7. Acharya Balkrishna et al., Vanshlochan Substitution and Adulteration: Discussions on the Controversy over its Original Source, *Ayushdhara*, July-August 2023, Vol 10, Issue 4, September 2023, ISSN: 2393-9583 (P)/ 2393- 9591 (O)
8. A.K. Gupta, Quality standards of indian medicinal plants, Indian council of medical research, Vol 1, P.n.97
9. A.K. Gupta, Quality standards of indian medicinal plants, Indian council of medical research, Vol 11, P.n.135